

Improve Professional Skills of Lecturers in the New Period In Line With the Development Strategy of the Economic and Technical College of Dien Bien

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1. Introduction

Higher education in Vietnam is in the transition period to find a suitable development path for domestic socio-economic conditions and international integration. One of the key issues of this process is the development of university lecturers. The teaching staff plays a decisive role in the quality of higher education. Dien Bien College of Economics and Engineering and one of the pioneers in comprehensive innovation. The school has been implementing the School Development Strategy for the period 2006-2020. The goal of the strategy is to bring Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology "Becoming a leading college providing high quality human resources to meet the increasing requirements for Dien Bien and Lai Chau provinces". In order to achieve that goal, it requires the staff and lecturers to be people with high professional skills and good professional skills to meet the strategic objectives set out. Training and research on occupational skills is a new field in Vietnam in general and in Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology in particular. Therefore, assessing the professional skills of lecturers and providing solutions to improve professional skills is essential.

2. Content

2.1. Current status of skills of lecturers of Dien Bien College of Economics and Technology

2.1.1. Skills of program development and document development

In this section there are 5 skills to be analyzed, which are: (1) Skills to learn information about learners' needs for disciplines and subjects; (2) Skills to develop training programs; (3) Skills to develop subject syllabus; (4) lesson planning skills; (5) Skills for writing lectures and textbooks.

Skills to learn information about learners' needs for majors and subjects. Skills to learn and synthesize information about teachers' needs of learners. The level of knowledge and proficiency is much higher than the level of knowledge and not known as Figure 01 below.

Figure 01: Skills to learn information about teachers' needs of learners

Teachers over 40 years of age at very high proficiency levels, this shows that teachers participate regularly in this activity and they are the most experienced group in understanding learners' needs for the discipline. It is worth emphasizing here that the teachers at all three ages are at a known level, accounting for between 35% and 43%. The age group under 30 and between 30 and 40 years old accounts for a high percentage of about 30% of the low level of knowledge and about 10% of the lecturers are at an unknown level. The comparison between female teachers and male lecturers shows that both female

and male lecturers have skills at a high level of relative knowledge and proficiency, with no big differences. The rate at which women know less is higher than male and does not know that women are also higher than men.

Skills to build training programs

The level of knowledge and proficiency is much higher than the level of knowledge and knowledge. However, there is a significant difference in the proficiency level between the age group 30 to 40 years old, which is 52.8% and under 30 years of age, only 7.2%. The comparison between female and male lecturers shows that both male and female teachers have the skills to develop training programs at a relatively high level of knowledge and proficiency and there is no big difference. This proves that both female and male teachers actively participate in training programs that have certain skills.

Skills to develop a subject syllabus

Group of trainers over 40 years old focus on the level of knowledge and proficiency is mainly accounted for 65%, especially emphasized that the group of lecturers under 30 also accounted for 60.7%. This proves that young lecturers have the opportunity to participate in the development of course syllabus as teachers at higher ages.

Lesson planning skills

Similar to the skill of developing a subject syllabus, the group of trainers focuses on knowledge and proficiency is mainly, especially the group of lecturers over 40 years old accounts for 78.9%, this shows that this group of lecturers There is a lot of experience in lesson planning. However, the percentage of lecturers under 30 also accounts for 62.5%, but very few of the young lecturers can participate in the course to develop lesson plans or lesson plans but mainly learn from lecturers. Experienced, so they are not self believe that lesson plans are effective in teaching.

Skills for writing lectures and textbooks

Similar to the above two skills, the group of trainers focuses on the level of knowledge and proficiency. Group of lecturers over 40 years old account for 70%, this explains the group of lecturers who have a lot of experience in writing lectures and textbooks. However, the proportion of faculty members under 30 also accounts for 62.5% but they mainly participate in translating textbooks and collecting materials.

2.1.2 Group of teaching and evaluation skills

This section is divided into 2 groups: teaching skills and assessment skills. Teaching skills include 5 skills, which are: (1) Skills to present and evoke problems; (2) Skills to use questions in teaching; (3) Skills to handle situations in teaching; (4) Skills of organizing and managing classes; (5) Skills of using teaching facilities. Assessment skills focus on 2 skills: 1) Skills to develop testing and evaluation criteria; (2) Skills to compile subject questions and exercises.

a. Teaching skills

Skills to present and evoke problems

The results showed that the group of trainers focused on the level of knowledge and proficiency. The group of teachers over 40 years old is proficient at 75%, similarly, the group of young lecturers under 30 years of age know well at 75%, this shows that young lecturers have good presentation skills and have A lot of effort in presenting and suggesting problems.

Skills to use questions in teaching

The group of trainers focuses on the level of knowledge and proficiency is mainly shown in Figure 02 below.

Figure 02: Skills to use questions in the teaching of teachers

From the above results, the group of over 40 years old is at the proficient level, accounting for 80%, similarly, the group of young lecturers under 30 years old knows well at 76.8%. Young lecturers share how much they use the question in teaching, yet they have questions at the level of comprehension and analysis, there are not many questions at a high level of thinking and still have difficulties while Ask questions accordingly and how to assess questions.

Skills to handle teaching situations

Similarly, the group of trainers focuses on the level of knowledge and proficiency. Group of lecturers over 40 years old at proficient rate accounted for 65%, but the group of young lecturers under 30 years old knew that the rate was higher than 80.4%. Although teachers have skills in handling situations with high rates, young lecturers often encounter dilemmas in class such as dealing with students' questions or dealing with communication situations in life, most are classes with older students.

Skills of organizing and managing classes

Two groups of lecturers aged 30 and above have the skills of organizing and managing class about 60% at a proficient level. However, lecturers also believe that it is effective to manage small classes; the management of large classes of over 100 students requires the support of tutors or departments.

Skills in using teaching facilities

Group of teachers from 30 to 40 years of age are more proficient in using 2 other groups. This shows that this group of lecturers has access to information technology and applies it to teaching. The opinions of older lecturers suggest that some young lecturers depend too much on using projectors in class so they are not flexible in teaching. This shows that the need for training in teaching methods is essential for young lecturers. The question is how to incorporate the methods in an appropriate and effective way without depending too much on the tools used.

b) Assessment skills

Skills to develop test and evaluation criteria

The results show that the proportion of lecturers at the level of knowledge and proficiency is quite high. However, in reality, the new lecturers stop at the qualitative assessment, there is no quantitative assessment tool. 100% of all lecturers asked that evaluation skills training are essential.

Skills to compile questions and exercise exercises

The proportion of lecturers at the level of knowledge and proficiency is quite high. This result is easy to understand because this is a regular task of teachers. However, lecturers believe that to compile questions at a high level of thinking in order to encourage learners to go to the learning process is difficult because it has not been trained; this skill relates to the questioning skills in the lecture. In the previous section, focusing on developing multiple choice questions also needs experience. This shows that the need for training on how to ask questions and compose questions is essential.

2.1.3. Group of scientific research skills

Group of scientific research skills (Scientific Research) includes 5 skills: (1) Skills to find and select scientific research topics; (2) Skills for writing scientific research protocols; (3) Skills to collect information and data when implementing scientific research topics; (4) Skills of processing information and data in scientific research; (5) Skills for writing scientific research reports.

Skills to find and select scientific research topics

The percentage of lecturers at a high level of knowledge in all 3 ages is above 50%, especially the group of lecturers from 30 to 40 years old account for 69.8%, the rate of lecturers at the proficiency level is much lower. a lot of. The group of young lecturers at a low level also accounts for 33.9%.

Skills for writing scientific research protocols

The proportion of lecturers at a high level of knowledge in all 3 ages is above 50%, especially the group of lecturers from 30 to 40 years old account for 66%, the rate of lecturers at the proficiency level is much lower. The group of young lecturers at a low level also accounts for 32.1%.

Figure 03: Skills for writing research outline of lecturers

This result also reflects that scientific research activities are relatively difficult for teachers. The lecturers all said that writing skills for scientific research are an important skill to be able to participate in scientific research topics.

Skills to collect and process information and data when implementing scientific research topics. The proportion of lecturers at a high level of knowledge in all 3 ages is above 50% in both skills. The lecturers said that when participating in scientific research, most lecturers have the skills to collect and process information within the scientific research topic.

Skills in writing scientific research reports

The proportion of lecturers at a high level of knowledge in all 3 ages is above 50%, especially young lecturers to 62.5%. Teachers believe that there are many opportunities to write scientific reports such as attending scientific conferences or writing articles published in scientific journals. However, more than 20% of young lecturers have never written scientific articles or reports. They all want to have the opportunity to participate in scientific research activities to enhance their expertise.

2.2. Factors affecting the teacher's skill status

The reasons for the situation of unskilled skills are given as follows: due to the heavy work leading to the lack of time to improve skills, it is difficult to apply skills in practice (large classes, facilities do not allow), no conditions for learning/lack of information materials, no regulations to force the application of positive teaching methods, so teachers have not really tried to apply, are not aware of the importance of skills. In addition, a number of other reasons are given: older lecturers are afraid to change, young lecturers have not been trained in active teaching skills and taught after a while in school, not yet available. Compulsory regulations on recruitment of pedagogical certificate requirements, there is no proper investment in teaching methods. Besides, the lecturers' income is low so it is not enough to encourage teachers to apply positive teaching methods.

2.3 Proposing solutions to improve the skills of teaching staff

The proposed solutions are based on 3 groups: expert group, management staff, lecturers and research team.

Proposals towards the school and departments:

Develop plans to improve professional qualifications and occupational skills, with a focus on integrating professional skills for young lecturers. Develop regulations on recruitment of professional skills requirements for newly recruited teachers and regulations for teachers in general. Establishing a board of advisors on teaching skills for teachers, implementing and monitoring periodically. To send lecturers to participate in training courses related to the teaching of prestigious domestic and international organizations, approach positive teaching methods. Organize seminars, seminars on teaching skills, invite outside experts to teach and share experiences. Organize training on teaching skills integrated into professional for young lecturers.

Organize intensive skills courses focusing on skills such as developing lesson plans (scenarios); design questions and situations in teaching; develop evaluation criteria; write a lecture. Towards the faculties and departments. Organize seminars/seminars on intensive teaching skills, invite experienced professional lecturers to exchange and share with young lecturers; Coordinating with schools and departments in organizing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating workshops and seminars to improve teaching skills. Create opportunities for young lecturers to participate in domestic and international projects to improve professional capacity associated with scientific research and access to positive teaching methods. In the above solutions, the school has invited international experts to teach teaching and presentation skills, which are evaluated by teachers effectively.

3. Conclusion

From the research results analyzed, the thesis draws some conclusions as follows. The difference in skills of teachers of Dien Bien College of Economics and Engineering at different ages clearly shows that lecturers have many years of teaching experience with teaching and scientific research skills. Better than young lecturers. Both male and female teachers have the skills to develop curriculum and teaching skills, but male teachers have better research skills than female teachers. The main factors affecting the current situation of teachers' skills are difficult to apply in practice because of the large class conditions, lecturers have not properly invested because of many jobs, lecturers have not been trained in teaching skills basic teaching and no compulsory regulations apply. Solutions made by a group of experts and managers, groups of lecturers and student groups to improve teaching skills for lecturers focusing on skill sets to develop programs, teaching skills, and skills scientific research.

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